

**ENHANCING WILLINGNESS TO COMMUNICATE: EXPLORING THE
FLIPPED CLASSROOM MODEL FOR LANGUAGE TEACHERS**

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Abstract: *This article examines the synergy between willingness to communicate and the flipped classroom model in language education. It explores the factors influencing willingness to communicate and provides practical strategies for fostering a supportive communicative environment. Additionally, it explores the implementation of the flipped classroom model as a means to enhance student engagement and language proficiency. The article highlights the importance of creating student-centered learning experiences that promote active communication and offers insights and recommendations for language teachers seeking to optimize their instructional practices.*

Keywords: *willingness to communicate, language education, flipped classroom model, student engagement, communicative environment, language proficiency, instructional practices.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается синергия между готовностью к общению и моделью «перевернутого класса» в языковом образовании. В нем исследуются факторы, влияющие на желание общаться, и предлагаются практические стратегии по созданию благоприятной коммуникативной среды. Кроме того, в нем исследуется реализация модели «перевернутого класса» как средства повышения вовлеченности учащихся и повышения уровня владения языком. В статье подчеркивается важность создания ориентированного на учащихся опыта обучения, который способствует активному общению, а также предлагаются идеи и рекомендации для учителей языка, стремящихся оптимизировать свою учебную практику.*

Ключевые слова: *готовность к общению, языковое образование, модель «перевернутого класса», вовлеченность учащихся, коммуникативная среда, владение языком, педагогическая практика.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola til ta'limida muloqot qilishga tayyorlik va teskari sinf modeli o'rtasidagi sinergiyani o'rganadi. U muloqot qilish istagiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillarni o'rganadi va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi kommunikativ muhitni yaratish uchun amaliy strategiyalarni taqdim etadi. Bundan tashqari, u o'quvchilarning faolligini va tilni bilish darajasini oshirish vositasi sifatida aylantirilgan sinf modelini amalga oshirishni o'rganadi. Maqolada faol muloqotni rag'batlantiradigan talabaga*

yo‘naltirilgan ta‘lim tajribasini yaratish muhimligi ta‘kidlanadi va o‘quv amaliyotlarini optimallashtirishga intilayotgan til o‘qituvchilari uchun tushuncha va tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *muloqotga tayyorlik, til ta‘limi, teskari sinf modeli, o‘quvchilarning faolligi, kommunikativ muhit, tilni bilish, o‘qitish amaliyoti.*

Every year there are new approaches to the organization of the educational process, most of which are closely related to the development of innovative technologies. The teacher constantly has to look for new methods and forms of conducting a lesson, to combine various educational technologies in order to make the learning process interesting, exciting, accessible, understandable and effective. The modern educational process takes into account both the trends in the development of science and technology, and the requirements of society for the quality of educational services. Therefore, today the teacher’s special attention is drawn to the metasubjective results of their educational activities, which provide the formation of universal learning activities, the development of personal qualities and the general culture of a student, an understanding of the value of education, motivation and responsibility for their learning.

In this regard, there are tasks: how to create a situation of open communication in the lesson, to allow each student to show initiative, independence, selectivity in the ways of activity?

One of the most effective ways to solve this problem can be considered the purposeful use of new teaching methods in educational establishments using information and communication technologies and electronic means. Given the pace of development of cloud technologies, the unlimited possibilities of cloud-oriented learning environments, ICTs allow not only to diversify the educational process, but also to introduce new teaching methods.

In the practice of educational technology, active teaching methods are becoming increasingly popular, ensuring the active and meaningful participation of each student in the learning process. Flipped Classroom is unlike traditional methods of pedagogy, which mostly focuses on the transfer of knowledge, active methods focus mainly on problem solving and teamwork skills. Samah Zakareya Ahmad lists different names from various empirical studies of the flipped classroom—sometimes called reverse, backwards, inverted, and upside down classroom—is an instructional model that inverts the traditional lecture-plus homework format. In this article Flipped Classroom (FC) term will be used.

In a flipped classroom, lectures are removed, and the removed content is often delivered to students through pre-class input materials like video recordings. Students can study various types of materials (e.g., readings from a textbook and worksheets developed by their teacher) on their own outside of class time and grasp the meaning

of the content. [1,63] Al-Harbi and Alshumaimeri explain the flipped classroom strategy is a pedagogical model in which lesson content is learned at home by means of technology, allowing teachers to devote class time to practicing lesson content with exercises, activities, discussions, or projects.[2,601]

The study of flipped classrooms was based on the theory of Bloom’s revised taxonomy of cognitive domain. This taxonomy provides six levels of learning. The explanation is arranged from the lowest level to the highest level:

1. Remembering: in this stage, the students try to recognize and recall the information they receive; they also try to understand the basic concepts and principles of the content they have learned.
2. Understanding: the students try to demonstrate their understanding, interpret the information and summarize what they have learned.
3. Applying: the students practice what they have learned or apply knowledge to the actual situation.
4. Analyzing: the students use their critical thinking in solving the problem, debate with friends, compare the answer with peers, and produce a summary. The students obtain new knowledge and ideas after implementing critical thinking or a debate in group activities. In this level of learning, the students also produce creative thinking.
5. Evaluating: assessment or established peer-review knowledge, judge in relational terms; in this stage, students are evaluating the whole learning concepts and they could evaluate or make judgment on how far they successfully learned.
6. Creating: the students are able to design, construct and produce something new from what they have learned. [3,17]

Zamzami and Siti show that flipped classroom suggests to have remembering and understanding as the lowest levels of cognitive domain which are practiced outside the class hour . While inclass time is spent higher forms of cognitive work, including applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating. With the flipped model, the lower levels are presented before class through recorded lectures and video. Readings, simulations, and other materials also provide this foundational support for learning so that in-class time can be spent working on higher levels of learning from application to evaluation. In flipped classrooms, students go from the lowest level (remembering) to achieve the highest level (creating). Implementing flipped learning allows the students to spend more time supporting higher-level learning tasks such as a group discussion, while lower-level tasks such as knowledge and comprehension are completed independently outside the class.[4,316]

Many instructors and researchers have discussed the benefits of flipped learning. As Hung notes in his one the articles that FC instruction has been implemented in various disciplines however in the field of language education empirical evidence on the effectiveness of FC is relatively scarce due to the fact that

most contemporary language courses are not taught using teacher centered approaches. Many proponents have claimed numerous advantages for the flipped classroom approach when applied in language teaching contexts, and one major benefit of flipping a language classroom is that teachers can reduce class time spent on input-oriented tasks (e.g., explaining vocabulary to enhance students’ video comprehension) and increase that spent on output-oriented tasks (e.g., having students work in small groups for video-based discussion). The body of literature on flipped language classrooms, while still limited, has started to grow in recent years. Within these pioneering studies, various technological tools are employed to facilitate the teaching of different aspects of language.[5,17]

Samah Zakareya Ahmad has found evidence from other empirical researches that FC increases students' academic performance, creates an environment that responds to their, and provides a content that is designed according to their needs. Moreover, the use of video puts lectures under the learners’ control, allowing them to watch, rewind, and fast-forward as they need. This makes content more accessible for students who cannot attend class as well as for students with accessibility concerns. Moreover, the flipped classroom increases students’ engagement, freedom, control, responsibility for learning, autonomy, collaboration, motivation, and confidence. It also changes students’ attitudes toward learning, allows them to learn at their own pace, shifts them from passive to active learners, offers them flexibility, and gives greater ownership over their learning.[6,167]

In his another article Hung adopted the flipped classroom approach to construct a technology-enhanced language learning environment, featuring online lessons in the format of WebQuests, as a means to facilitate university students’ learning in an English communication course. The results suggested that, when structured and done well, flipped language classrooms could enhance students’ academic performance, participation levels, and learning attitudes in comparison to those seen in their counterparts in a control group. Arguably, technology plays an integral role in flipped language classrooms, with its potential to increase opportunities for learners to use the second language (L2) during the language learning process, both in and out of class. It is thus reasonable to envision that further advances in technology can contribute to the proliferation of the flipped classroom approach, both in language courses and in content courses more generally.[7,81]

The flipped classroom radically changed the traditional concept of teaching and learning by shifting how the teacher is teaching and the learners are learning. Giving students control over their learning is the revolutionary idea behind the flipped classroom strategy. In the EFL context, they believe the flipped classroom strategy can help solve common problems of English language learners, such as lack of

participation, communication, interaction opportunities, lack of sufficient feedback, and low proficiency levels.[2,601]

In Lee and Wallace's study, which was conducted at a South Korea University, I have found out that in an EFL situation, English is not used as a means of communication in society but taught as one of the school subjects. Thus, students have few opportunities to receive language input outside the classroom. Also, as is typical in many EFL classrooms, despite the screening process based on various types of placement tests, students' English ability varies. Moreover, many language instructors feel that there is insufficient class time to provide individualized feedback on students' work. To provide more language input and feedback for students, accommodate the variation in their levels, and facilitate the challenges of the English mediated lessons. By moving the lecture content outside class, we could give students more individualized feedback on their work in class that they might not otherwise receive, even in the CLT classroom. And this is the opportunity for instructors to act as a facilitator, a guide, and a resource, not merely as a lecturer, and to foster learner responsibility and participation was a large motivating factor in employing this new teaching methodology. In this study they mention that the FC helped closely examine their own teaching practice and reduce some level of anxiety and workload.[1,67]

To restate what has been said above the FC technology remarkably contributes to the creation of an open communication situation at the lesson, an individual approach organization, allows the teacher to increase the amount of information qualitatively, and the student to show initiative, autonomy, selectivity in the ways of working, and as a result, better prepare for the lesson. This organization of learning encourages students to learn from each other. The use of technology is aimed at their involvement in active learning activities. The FC helps increase the responsibility of students for their own learning which the main factor in the process of acquiring knowledge.

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